

ineffective. Carbofuran among insecticides and DBCP among nematicides were less effective than oxamyl or fensulfothion.

Inoculation of these larvae to roots of IR8 showed that root invasion was impaired by treatments at sublethal concentrations of propanil, fensulfothion, and oxamyl at 25 ppm; and of DBCP, phorate, and chlorpyrifos (insecticides) at 100 ppm. Carbofuran at 200 ppm adversely affected the larval penetration although it gave less direct contact mortality. ZR-777 and Diethyl sulfate (hormones) were effective at 250 to 500 ppm and above, while quinalphos, mephospholan (insecticides), 2,4-D, butachlor, MCPA (herbicides), IAA, IBA, NAA, maleic hydrazide, and gibberellic acid (growth regulators) had no persistent or inhibitory toxicity.

Soildrench pesticide treatment to control the root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne graminicola*

K. S. Krishna Prasad and Y. S. Rao,
Central Rice Research Institute,
Cuttack 753006, India

Twelve pesticides were tested as postinoculation soil-drench treatments for effectiveness in control of the root-knot nematode *M. graminicola*. The doses 25, 50, 100, and 200 ppm were adjusted to 3.75 to 30 kg/ha. Phorate, oxamyl, fensulfothion, and carbofuran were significantly superior to DBCP, chlorpyrifos, quinalphos, and emphospholan. The fungicides mebenil, bavistin, thiabendazole, and cela-50 were less effective. Oxamyl and fensulfothion at 50 ppm and above, and DBCP and phorate at 100 ppm, were equally effective in reducing egg masses and endoparasites. Carbofuran significantly controlled egg mass production.

Preplanting and postplanting soil-drench treatments in the fields showed that oxamyl, phorate, carbofuran, and fensulfothion at 15 kg/ha were equally effective in reducing the development of the nematodes and the production of egg masses in roots. These treatments markedly reduced the larval population in the soils regardless of time of application. Oxamyl and fensulfothion

inhibited giant cell development at sites of nematode establishment. The dimensions of the giant cells and

developing nematodes were reduced in the postplanting soil application of these systemic pesticides.

Pest management and control WEEDS

Sensitivity of rice field alga *Chara* sp. to different chemicals

D. C. Khatua, S. Maiti, and N. Mukherjee,
Department of Plant Pathology, Bidhan
Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani,
West Bengal, India

Green algae of different morphology and growth habit and belonging to different genera grow extensively in transplanted paddy fields in India; the most common is *Chara* sp. These organisms not only compete with rice plants for space and nutrients but appear to hinder tillering. Use of copper sulfate and other chemicals for their control has not been successful.

Some fungicides, insecticides, and synthetic detergents were screened for

algicidal activity against *Chara* grown in waterlogged soil in pots. The water was replaced with chemical treatments of desired concentration and the time required for complete alga death was recorded. Nine of 16 fungicides were good inhibitors at low concentration. They include the organic tin compounds Brestan 60 and Brestanol (see table). The carbamates Dithane M-45 and TMTD were found to be inhibitory even at 0.007% concentration. Among the insecticides and detergents, thiodan and the two detergents are equally inhibitory. The algicidal properties of these chemicals at such low concentrations are encouraging.

Algicidal activity of some fungicides, insecticides, and other chemicals against *Chara* sp. (av. of four replications). West Bengal, India.

Chemical	Days after treatment until death at percent concentration of whole formulation							
	1	0.5	0.25	0.12	0.06	0.03	0.015	0.007
<i>Fungicides</i>								
Blotox-50	2	2	3	3	4	4	4	ND ^a
Dithane 2-78	1	1	2	4	5	6	ND	
Dithane M-45	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	4
TMTD 75WPP	1	1	1	2	2	2	4	4
Starcraft 83WP	2	2	2	2	2	3	4	ND
Difolatan 80WP	1	1	1	2	2	3	3	4
Brestanol45	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	3
Brestan 60	1	1	1	1	2	2	3	3
Brassicol 75WP	2	2	2	3	3	4	5	ND
Hinosan 50EC	ND							
Bavistin	ND							
Topsin M	ND							
Allisan	ND							
Benodanil	ND							
Kasumin	ND							
<i>Insecticides and other chemicals</i>								
Thiodan 35EC	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3
Accothon 1000	1	1	2	2	3	4	ND	
Diazinon G.	2	3	ND					
Disyston G.	ND							
Sultaf. 80WP	ND							
Idet-20	0.5	0.5	1	1	2	2	3	3
Swascifix 45	0.5	0.5	1	1	2	2	3	3
Det. (Washing)	1	1	1	1	2	2	4	ND
Copper sulfate	1	2	2	3	3	3	4	4

^aND = no death.